

Ōzaki Shinryū, Shakuhachi, Komusō, Shingū, and the Formation of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū

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Abstract

This article reconsiders Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎真龍), a figure often mentioned but rarely examined closely in the history of Myōan-related shakuhachi. It argues that Ōzaki is best understood neither as a securely documented abbot of Myōan-ji nor as the simple founder of a fully formed modern school. Rather, he stands at a point where several histories meet: older Myōan repertory, the collapse of the Fuke institutional order, local memory in Shingū, Katsuura Shōzan's transmission, and the later canonization of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū. The article brings together materials that have usually been treated apart: Riley Lee's critique of retrospective shakuhachi historiography, Yukino Tomoko's manuscript-based work on the Shinpō corpus, local memorial and epigraphic evidence from Shingū, fieldwork conducted by the author in June 2025, Tsukamoto Kodō's 1978 report on the dedication of the Ōzaki memorial stone, and late source editions connected with Katsuura Shōzan. A comparison with recent research on the Akutami conflict and other local Fuke institutions further sharpens the argument. It shows that late Fuke history cannot be written from musical lineage alone, but must also attend to temple authority, local jurisdiction, mobility, administrative control, and the later work of memory. Ōzaki thus appears not as a solitary founder, but as a historically recoverable mediator between an older temple-linked world and the later forms of repertorial preservation, textual stabilization, and memorial canonization through which the Myōan Shinpō-ryū became visible.

Keywords: Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎真龍); Myōan Shinpō-ryū (明暗真法流); Myōan-ji (明暗寺); Fuke sect (普化宗); Komusō (虚無僧); Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山); Shingū (新宮); Zenryū-ji (全龍寺); yakusō (役僧); honkyoku (本曲); local memory; memorialization.

1. Introduction

Shakuhachi historiography has long occupied an uneasy place between music history, religious history, lineage memory, and local commemoration. The instrument's association with komusō (虚無僧), honkyoku (本曲), Zen discourse, and the abolition of the Fuke sect (普化宗, Fuke-shū) in 1871 has produced a substantial body of writing, but not a stable method. Some works preserve valuable transmission memory; others repeat school claims, temple legends, or late commemorative formulas with too little source criticism. Riley Lee's dissertation remains a necessary starting point because it treats shakuhachi history as a problem of transmission and variation, rather than as a simple succession of schools.¹

Later scholarship has made that instability still clearer. Tsukitani, Seyama, Shimura, and Lee describe a field shaped by change, diversification, locality, and competing repertorial identities.² Yukino Tomoko's dissertation is especially important for the present article because it turns from broad lineage history to manuscript criticism. Her work shows that the materials later gathered under the name Shinpō-ryū or Myōan Shinpō-ryū are older and

more layered than a founder narrative would allow. Much of the repertory points back to older Kyoto Myōan-related transmission, while the explicit school identity appears to have stabilized only later.³

The same problem appears in sharper form around Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎真龍), the local setting of Shingū (新宮), and the later visibility of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū (明暗真法流). In English-language scholarship, Ōzaki has remained a small but troublesome figure. Lee records the later tradition that connects him with the Myōan Shinpō line and with Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山), but also corrects the older claim that he was the thirty-fifth abbot of Myōan-ji. That correction is crucial. It removes a convenient institutional biography without making Ōzaki historically irrelevant.⁴

This article begins from that tension. Ōzaki should not be presented as a securely documented abbot of Myōan-ji, nor as the founder of a fully formed school in the later sense. He is better understood as a figure through whom several strands of evidence meet: a secular identity, a komusō name, a temple-functionary title, local memorial reconstruction in Shingū, and transmission memory connected with Katsuura Shōzan. The central question, then, is not whether Ōzaki “founded” the Myōan Shinpō-ryū in a simple institutional sense. It is how older Myōan-related repertory and memory became visible, after the collapse of the Fuke order, as the later Myōan Shinpō-ryū.

2. State of Research and the Akutami Comparison

Shakuhachi scholarship is most useful for the present problem where it treats school names with caution. Lee’s work remains important because it shows how often shakuhachi sources are retrospective, school-specific, or shaped by insider memory. Yukino Tomoko brings that caution to the Shinpō materials themselves. Her dissertation suggests that the question is not whether a fixed Myōan Shinpō-ryū existed unchanged from an earlier period, but how a body of repertoire, notation, and memory came to be named and stabilized over time.³

The Akutami materials provide a comparative frame for that problem. They belong to another region and another dispute, but they clarify the institutional world in which late Fuke identities operated. Kitō Katsuyuki’s work on the Akutami Komusō conflict, together with local histories of Reihō-ji and Ichigetsu-ji and the author’s separate study of the case, shows that Fuke history cannot be reduced to musical lineage or Zen vocabulary. It also involved itinerant privilege, temple jurisdiction, village burden, stop-place rights (tomeba 留場), local officials, and administrative suspicion. The Akutami evidence is especially useful because it keeps apart institutions that later writing can blur: Kyoto Myōan-ji, Otoguro Meian-ji, Fudai-ji, Reihō-ji/Katsusō-ha, and Ichigetsu-ji/Kinsen-ha cannot be treated as interchangeable signs of “Fuke” authority.⁵

The comparison does not make Ōzaki part of the Akutami conflict. Its value is methodological. It changes the questions asked of the Ōzaki materials. When the Zenryū-ji inscription calls Ōzaki a yakusō (役僧) of Kyoreizan Myōan-ji (虚靈山明暗寺), that term should be read against a world in which temple office, authorization, mobility, local memory, and musical authority were entangled. Likewise, “komusō name” should not be flattened into a romantic image of a wandering mendicant monk. In late Edo and early Meiji contexts, komusō identity could overlap with secular status, performance practice, institutional service, and regional reputation.

Hosaka Hirooki’s work on the dismantling of the Fuke sect strengthens this perspective at the macrohistorical level. Lee already stresses that the abolition ended an institution without extinguishing shakuhachi practice. Hosaka helps explain why that institutional end mattered: it dismantled a privileged frame that had organized movement, protection, affiliation, and claims to authority. Read together with Yukino’s manuscript evidence, this makes the Ōzaki-Katsuura line more intelligible. Older Myōan-related repertory survived, but it did so after the institutional world that had carried it had been weakened or dissolved.^{6,7}

3. Sources and Method

This article works with sources of different weight and different purpose. Some provide the main argument; others help with orientation, names, dates, or local context. The first group consists of modern scholarship on shakuhachi transmission and the Fuke sect, especially Lee, Yukino, and Hosaka. These works provide the interpretive frame, but they do not by themselves establish the biographical details of Ōzaki's life.

A second group consists of late printed and memorial-source materials, especially Katsuura Seizan Ifu (勝浦正山遺譜), writings associated with Inagaki Ihaku, and Tsukamoto Kodō's short report on the 1978 dedication of the Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone. These sources are indispensable for understanding how the Ōzaki-Katsuura legacy was preserved, organized, and publicly commemorated in the twentieth century. At the same time, they must be kept distinct from nineteenth-century evidence.

The local evidence from Shingū forms a third and particularly important group: the Zenryū-ji memorial stone, the grave-side signboard near Shinnyo-ji, the cemetery map, and the municipal signboard concerning the former Horiuchi residence site. These sources are not of equal strength. For example, the 1978 memorial stone is stronger than the grave-side signboard for Ōzaki's death date because its profile is denser and internally more coherent. Even so, it remains a modern commemorative inscription, not direct proof from the Bakumatsu or early Meiji period.^{8,9}

This local layer was examined directly during fieldwork in Shingū in June 2025. The purpose of the visit was not simply to collect photographs, but to test how textual claims, surviving inscriptions, public signboards, and the physical arrangement of the memorial landscape relate to one another. The author documented the Zenryū-ji memorial setting, the Ōzaki Shinryū commemorative stone, the municipal signboard for the former Horiuchi residence site, the grave-side signboard near Shinnyo-ji, and the cemetery map identifying Ōzaki's grave. This made it possible to compare the wording of the 1978 stone, the grave-side public explanation, Tsukamoto's dedication report, and later printed accounts of Ōzaki's rediscovery against the local topography itself.

Finally, the article uses reference works and online catalogues, including Kotobank, National Diet Library records, public tourism and prefectural pages, and local administrative websites. These are useful for orientation, spelling, names, dates, and public-history statements, but they do not carry the main historical argument.¹⁰

The source hierarchy also shapes the language of the article. Claims based on direct inscriptional evidence are stated more firmly than claims preserved only in later local narrative. Claims about arrest, political activity, confinement (幽閉, yūhei), 300-koku status, or the exact rediscovery process of the grave remain cautious unless supported by stronger documentary evidence. The aim is not to strip the tradition of meaning, but to let each source speak at the level it can sustain.

4. Shingū, Kumano, and the Post-Fuke Setting

Ōzaki Shinryū cannot be reconstructed from shakuhachi lineage materials alone. His later memory is tied to Shingū, a city whose history belongs to the wider religious geography of Kumano. Shingū formed part of the sacred landscape of the Kumano Sanzan (熊野三山) and lay on pilgrimage routes now grouped under Kumano Kodō (熊野古道), including Ogumotori-goe (大雲取越), Kogumotori-goe (小雲取越), Kōya-zaka (高野坂), and the river route down the Kumano-gawa (熊野川).¹¹

Within Shingū, Zenryū-ji (全龍寺) occupies a site with its own local history. The municipal signboard issued by the Shingū City Board of Education identifies the temple precinct and its surroundings as the former residence grounds of the Horiuchi family (堀内氏屋敷跡), a local power active from the Sengoku period into the beginning of the early modern era. Citing the Kii zoku fudoki (紀伊続風土記), the signboard notes the scale of the former site and the remains of its moats. It therefore places Zenryū-ji within a local history that long predates the modern commemoration of Ōzaki.

This setting matters, but it should not be made to prove too much. The Horiuchi signboard does not establish any direct biographical fact about Ōzaki. It does show, however, that the memorial site later associated with him stood in a place already marked by temple history, civic memory, and the older political landscape of Shingū. Shingū Castle, built between 1619 and 1633 and dismantled by 1875, provides the early modern political frame within which local warrior and temple histories later became legible.¹²

The larger break came with the abolition of the Fuke sect in 1871. Read through Lee, Hosaka, and the Akutami comparison, this was not simply the end of a formal sectarian status. It was the dismantling of a practical order that had joined temple affiliation, permission to move, claims to religious identity, musical authority, and forms of social protection. Ōzaki's significance lies at this point of transition. He is remembered where an older Myōan-linked institutional world could no longer sustain itself in its previous form, while its repertoire, names, and authority were recast through later teachers, manuscripts, and memorial acts.^{6,7}

Figure 1. Zenryū-ji / Shingū memorial setting. Photograph from the author's fieldwork, June 2025.

Figure 2. Zenryū-ji / Shingū memorial setting. Photograph from the author's fieldwork, June 2025.

5. Zenryū-ji: Signboard, Memorial Stone, and Local Memory

The local evidence at Zenryū-ji combines two different kinds of source. The municipal signboard concerning the Horiuchi residence site situates the place within the older history of Shingū. The modern memorial stone for Ōzaki Shinryū, by contrast, gives the strongest local formulation of his remembered identity.

The memorial stone identifies him as Ōzaki Uemon (尾崎卯右衛門), sixth son of Ōzaki Sōsuke (尾崎宗助), born in Shingū on the second day of the ninth month of Bunsei 3 (1820), and deceased on the thirty-first day of the eighth month of Meiji 21 (1888). It describes him as “yakusō of Kyoreizan Myōan-ji” (虚靈山明暗寺役僧), gives his komusō name as Ōzaki Shinryū (虚無僧名 尾崎真龍), names Zenryū-ji as his bodai-ji (菩提寺 全龍寺), and presents him as revered as a founding figure of the shakuhachi tradition of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū. The inscription also records that the monument was erected in Shōwa 53 (1978), with the text composed by Inagaki Ihaku (稲垣衣白).⁸

The inscription is valuable because it gathers in one place Ōzaki’s secular identity, family relation, temple-functionary status, komusō name, memorial temple, and later school memory. Its limits are just as important. Since it was erected in 1978, it cannot be read as a contemporary nineteenth-century document. The title yakusō is strong evidence for how Ōzaki was remembered within a Myōan institutional frame; the phrase “revered as founder,” by contrast, is better read as memorial language than as proof that he founded a fully articulated modern school in his lifetime.

The term yakusō (役僧) is therefore crucial. It does not mean abbot. It points instead to a monk or religious functionary entrusted with practical, administrative, or official duties within a temple setting. In the present case, the term supports a careful middle position: Ōzaki was remembered as holding a formal Myōan-related role, but the evidence does not justify restoring the older claim that he was a numbered abbot of Myōan-ji.

6. Tsukamoto's 1978 Dedication Report: Ceremony, Memory, and a Problematic Toponym

Tsukamoto Kodō's 1978 account of the dedication of the Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone deserves separate treatment. It is not a biographical source in the narrow sense, but a record of how Ōzaki was publicly commemorated in Shingū in the late twentieth century. Entitled “Ōzaki Shinryū-shi kenshōhi konryū” (尾崎真竜師顕彰碑建立), the report states that the dedication and unveiling were held on 2 October 1978. Tsukamoto presents the monument as honoring Ōzaki for transmitting the classical honkyoku repertory of Kyoto Myōan-ji to Katsuura Shōzan. He also notes that the ceremony took place in fine weather and drew substantial local and Myōan-related participation.¹⁶

The gathering brought together several overlapping circles: local Shingū actors involved in the recovery of Ōzaki's memory, representatives of tea-cultural networks, and members of the modern Myōan shakuhachi world. Tsukamoto names Sugimoto Yoshio (杉本義夫), also identified as Sōju (宗珠), as a local historian and one of the figures involved in the discovery of the grave. This matters because the memorial inscription names Sugimoto Sōju (杉本宗珠) as the calligrapher of the stone. The report also mentions members of the Urasenke Tankōkai Nanki Branch, Hirasumi Eun (平住恵雲), priest of Myōan-ji, Kojima Issui (児島一吹), and numerous members of the Myōan Dōshu-kai, several of whom attended in komusō dress. Inagaki Ihaku (稲垣衣白) from Toyota and Ishizuna Seiho (石綱清圃) from Kanuma are also listed among the participants.

The rite itself is described as a Buddhist dedication accompanied by shakuhachi performance. At the appointed time, komusō-style flute playing opened the proceedings. Araki Yūhō (荒木裕鳳), named as the officiating priest, presided, while Sugimoto removed the covering from the monument. The ceremony included an “eye-opening incense verse” (開眼香語), a dedicatory text that ritually activated the stone and placed Ōzaki within a religious and musical frame. Tsukamoto reproduces this text in classical Chinese style. Its language presents Ōzaki as an exceptional figure within the Fuke/Myōan world and links him to a form of shakuhachi transmission understood as more than ordinary performance. The wording is commemorative rather than documentary, but it is valuable precisely for that reason: it shows how Ōzaki was elevated ritually and rhetorically at the moment of public memorialization.

After the unveiling and dedication, the participants reportedly held a discussion meeting on Ōzaki's life and achievements. Tsukamoto concludes that Shingū had gained a new local object of pride. This detail is important for the present study because the event did not merely honor a stable, already self-evident historical figure. It helped produce Ōzaki as a public local figure. The stone, the ceremony, the participation of local historians and shakuhachi practitioners, and the language of the dedication all show how Ōzaki's modern profile was reconstructed at the intersection of local history, Buddhist commemoration, and Myōan-lineage memory.

At the same time, Tsukamoto's account must be used with caution. It prints the location as “Kinryūji-machi” and “Kinryū-ji” (金竜寺町／金竜寺), although the extant memorial inscription identifies Ōzaki's bodaiji as Zenryū-ji (菩提寺 全龍寺), and other local evidence also points to Zenryū-ji in Shingū. Present official postal-address data for Shingū do not list a Kinryūji-machi. The printed 金竜寺 is therefore best treated as a probable typographical or editorial error for 全龍寺. This does not weaken the report as evidence for the 1978 ceremony, but it does prevent its place-name wording from being used uncritically as topographical evidence.

7. The Grave and the Twentieth-Century Rediscovery

The grave-site signboard and cemetery map near Shinnyo-ji form a second body of local evidence. They place Ōzaki within a wider public landscape of notable graves in Shingū and identify his grave as part of a local historical route. The signboard repeats several details also found on the Zenryū-ji stone: birth in Shingū, the secular name Ōzaki Uemon, performance of honkyoku from the Myōan-ji tradition, and transmission to Katsuura Shōzan.⁹

For chronology, however, the grave-side sign is weaker than the Zenryū-ji inscription. It gives Meiji 22 (1889) and says that Ōzaki died at the age of seventy. The age itself is not necessarily mistaken: if read as traditional Japanese age reckoning (数え年, *kazoe-doshi*), it is consistent with a birth in Bunsei 3 (1820) and death in 1889. The difficulty is the year. The Zenryū-ji memorial stone gives Meiji 21 (1888), and its dating is tied to a fuller and more internally coherent memorial profile. For that reason, the 1888 date should be preferred unless stronger evidence appears.

The modern recovery of Ōzaki's grave appears to have involved both shakuhachi-related researchers and local historical inquiry in Shingū. Later Japanese discussion reports that Inagaki Ihaku, troubled by the lack of secure birth and death dates, contacted Shingū municipal authorities and, with the assistance of Sugimoto Yoshio (杉本義夫), examined removed household-register entries until Ōzaki Uemon was identified as the historical person behind Ōzaki Shinryū. Kunimi also cites a 1977 Geinō Shinpō report stating that Sugimoto had located the joint grave of Ōzaki and his wife.¹³

This stage of the evidence remains indirect until the original Geinō Shinpō issue is inspected. Even so, the reported sequence helps explain why the 1978 Zenryū-ji inscription contains such a coherent civil and memorial profile. The stone does not merely preserve inherited memory. It also records the outcome of a twentieth-century act of recovery: Ōzaki was made visible again through local investigation, inscription, and public commemoration.

8. From Ōzaki to Katsuura Shōzan

Ōzaki's historical role becomes clearest in relation to Katsuura Shōzan. Lee places both men within the later Myōan Shinpō tradition. Later shakuhachi-oriented discussion, drawing in part on materials attributed to Takahashi Kūzan, places Katsuura's study under Ōzaki roughly between April 1883 and November 1887. In that reconstruction, Katsuura studied under "Ōzaki Shinryū, who had been a yakusō of Kyoto Myōan-ji," and received the Myōan repertory in proper form.^{4, 13, 14}

The number of transmitted pieces varies across the sources. The grave-side sign gives fifty-nine honkyoku pieces; other later discussion expands the number to nearly seventy. These figures should not be treated as archival certainties. Their importance lies in the pattern they preserve: local and lineage-based sources consistently remember Ōzaki as the major transmitter of a substantial Myōan-derived repertory to Katsuura.

Yukino's dissertation makes this relation historically meaningful without turning it into a simple founder story. The Shinpō corpus is older and more internally layered than later school narratives imply, while the clearer name and identity of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū belong to a later phase of organization. In that sequence, Ōzaki represents the older transmission layer, still remembered through Myōan-ji and yakusō language. Katsuura represents the stage at which that inherited repertory became more visible as a named, teachable, and textually organized body of pieces.³

9. Katsuura Seizan Ifu and the Canonization of the Line

Katsuura Seizan Ifu (勝浦正山遺譜) is central to the argument, but it must be used for the right reason. It is not a nineteenth-century primary document and should not be asked to prove every biographical claim about Ōzaki. It is better understood as a late memorial-source edition centered on Katsuura Shōzan and shaped by the institutional memory of the later Myōan world.¹⁵

Its table of contents includes textual clusters that correspond closely to the materials analyzed by Yukino: Kodan Sankyokufu (古伝三曲譜), Sankyorei-fu (三虚霊譜), and Shinpō-ryū-fu I and II (真法流譜 (一) · (二)). This overlap matters because it shows that the repertorial groupings identified through manuscript study also survived as materially organized textual bodies within later memorial culture. The volume therefore helps explain canonization, not original foundation.

The evidence points to a layered sequence rather than a single founding act. Older Myōan-related repertory predates the later school label. Ōzaki is remembered as one of its key transmitters. Katsuura becomes the figure through whom that inheritance is consolidated and made teachable. Later printed and memorial editions then give the line a more stable textual and institutional form. This model fits the evidence better than a simple founder narrative, because it allows each source to do only the work it can actually support.

10. Conclusion

Ōzaki Shinryū matters because he resists the neat biography that later tradition sometimes seems to want from him. The evidence does not restore him as the thirty-fifth abbot of Myōan-ji. It also does not reduce him to a vague name in school memory. What can be reconstructed is more useful: a figure remembered through secular genealogy, komusō naming, temple function, local inscription, repertory transmission, and twentieth-century acts of recovery.

The strongest local anchor remains the Zenryū-ji memorial inscription. It identifies Ōzaki Uemon, sixth son of Ōzaki Sōsuke, as yakusō of Kyoreizan Myōan-ji and gives Ōzaki Shinryū as his komusō name. Since the stone was erected in 1978, it cannot be treated as a nineteenth-century document. Its importance lies elsewhere. It records the form in which local, familial, and Myōan-related memory had been gathered and made public in Shingū.

The Akutami comparison sharpens the larger point. Late Fuke history was not carried by musical lineage alone. It was embedded in institutions, local rights, administrative categories, movement, economic burden, and temple authority. After 1871, that world did not simply vanish. Parts of it were displaced, renamed, or reassembled. Names, repertoires, manuscripts, teachers, and memorial practices survived even as the older legal frame collapsed.

Ōzaki is best placed between these two historical orders. On one side stands the older Fuke/Myōan world of temple function, komusō identity, regulated movement, and institutional authority. On the other side stands the later world in which Myōan Shinpō-ryū became visible as a named repertorial and memorial formation. Katsuura Shōzan, Katsuura Seizan Ifu, and the Shingū memorial materials make the line legible; Ōzaki marks one of the points through which the older order passed into that later form.

The article's contribution is therefore not a heroic founding biography, but a source-critical reconstruction of a layered historical process: transmission, institutional collapse, local recovery, and canonization. On that evidence, Ōzaki Shinryū is best understood as a historically grounded mediator between Myōan-ji memory, Shingū local history, Katsuura Shōzan, and the later Myōan Shinpō-ryū.

Endnotes

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7. Hosaka Hirooki (保坂裕興), “Komusō—Fuke-shū wa dono yō ni kaitai shita ka” (虚無僧—普化宗はどのように解体したか), in Takano Toshihiko (高埜利彦), ed., *Minkan ni ikiru shūkyōsha (民間に生きる宗教者)* (Tokyo: Yoshikawa Kōbunkan, 2000); Hosaka Hirooki, “Fuke-shū haishi to kinsei ajiru no ichi tokushitsu” (普化宗廃止と近世アジールの一特質), 2012.
8. Zenryū-ji (全龍寺), “Ōzaki Shinryū-shi Kenshōhi” (尾崎真龍師顕彰碑), commemorative inscription, Shingū, erected 1978; photographed by the author, June 2025.
9. Grave-side explanatory signboard and cemetery map for Ōzaki Shinryū near Shinnyo-ji (真如寺), Shingū; photographed by the author, June 2025.
10. Kotobank entries for Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎真龍 / 尾崎真竜), Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山), and yakusō (役僧), accessed 2026.
11. Shingū City Tourist Association, “Kumano Kodō”; Shingū City Board of Education (新宮市教育委員会), “Shiseki Horiuchi-shi Yashiki Ato” (史跡 堀内氏屋敷跡), explanatory signboard at Zenryū-ji, installed June 2020 and photographed by the author, June 2025.
12. Japan Tourism Agency, “Shingū Castle Ruins”; Wakayama Prefecture, “Shingū-jō ato (Tanzaku-jō ato)” (新宮城跡 (丹鶴城跡)).
13. Kunimi Masafumi, “Kamigata no shakuhachi, sono jūsan: Katsuura Shōzan, sono ichi” (上方の尺八 その十三 ~勝浦正山 その一~), *Suitiku Hōgo (酔竹放語)*, 6 June 2020, addendum 1 July 2020. The Geinō Shinpō item on the rediscovery of Ōzaki’s grave is cited through Kunimi; the original issue has not yet been directly inspected.

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Appendix Introduction

The appendices gather the local and documentary materials on which the source-critical argument of the article depends. They are not intended to repeat the conclusion or to create a second narrative after the main text. Rather, they provide the evidentiary basis behind the article’s distinctions between secure evidence, later memorial reconstruction, and still uncertain tradition.

Appendices A–C present the field materials from Shingū: the municipal signboard at Zenryū-ji, the Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone, and the grave-side signboard near Shinryo-ji. These items preserve different layers of local memory, but they are not equally strong as historical evidence. For that reason, the appendices keep Japanese text, romanization, and English translation together, so that readers can see how each source has been used in the argument.

Appendix D offers a prosopographical register of the principal figures in the transmission and reconstruction of the Ōzaki material. Appendix E gives a working chronology. Both are included to keep the main article from becoming overloaded with evidentiary detail while still allowing the reader to trace names, dates, institutional roles, and unresolved points.

Appendix A. Shingū City Historical Signboard

Figure A1. Shingū City historical signboard at Zenryū-ji. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Japanese text

新宮市指定文化財

史跡 堀内氏屋敷跡

指定年月日 昭和39年(1964)6月8日

全龍寺と周辺は、戦国時代から近世初頭にかけて奥熊野地方を支配した堀内氏の屋敷地であった。江戸時代後期の『紀伊続風土記』には、周囲が五町(約550m)、四方に堀があったと記されており、現在、裏手(西方)と北方の一部にその名残の小川が残る。

堀内氏の出自は定かでないが、15世紀中頃から記録に現れる。16世紀半ば以降、堀内氏善の頃には、熊野速玉・熊野那智の社家と結びついて勢力を拡大、羽柴秀吉の紀州攻めには臣従し、熊野惣地の支配を許された。秀吉の朝鮮侵攻への従軍、京都・大坂への熊野材の輸送など、関ヶ原の戦いで西軍に参加し九州へ落ちのびるまで、この地を拠点に権勢を振るった。

ここは新宮が近世新宮城の城下町として整備される以前の歴史がうかがえる場所である。

令和2年(2020)6月
新宮市教育委員会

Romaji

Shingū-shi shitei bunkazai
Shiseki Horiuchi-shi yashiki ato
Shitei nengappi Shōwa sanjūkyū-nen (1964) rokugatsu yōka

Zenryū-ji to shūhen wa, Sengoku jidai kara kinsei shotō ni kakete Oku-Kumano chihō o shihai shita Horiuchi-shi no yashikichi de atta. Edo jidai kōki no Kii zoku fudoki ni wa, shūi ga go-chō (yaku 550m), shihō ni hori ga atta to shirushite ari, genzai, urate (seihō) to hokuhō no ichibu ni sono nagori no ogawa ga nokoru.

Horiuchi-shi no shutsuji wa sadaka de nai ga, jūgo seiki chūgoro kara kiroku ni arawareru. Jūroku seiki nakaba ikō, Horiuchi Ujijoshi / Ujizen (reading uncertain) no koro ni wa, Kumano Hayatama, Kumano Nachi no shake to musubitsuite seiryoku o kakudai, Hashiba Hideyoshi no Kishū-zeme ni wa jūjun shi, Kumano sōchi no shihai o yurusareta. Hideyoshi no Chōsen shinkō e no jūgun, Kyōto, Ōsaka e no Kumano-zai no yusō nado, Sekigahara no tatakai de Seigun ni sankā shi Kyūshū e ochinobiru made, kono chi o kyoten ni kensei o furutta.

Koko wa Shingū ga kinsei Shingū-jō no jōkamachi to shite seibi sareru izen no rekishi ga ukagaeru basho de aru.

Reiwa ni-nen (2020) rokugatsu
Shingū-shi Kyōiku Iinkai

Direct English translation

Shingū City Designated Cultural Property
Historic Site: Former Residence Grounds of the Horiuchi Family
Date of Designation: 8 June 1964

Zenryū-ji and its surrounding area were the residential grounds of the Horiuchi family, who ruled the Oku-Kumano region from the Sengoku period into the beginning of the early modern period. The late Edo-period Kii zoku fudoki records that the site measured five chō in circumference (approximately 550 meters) and was surrounded by moats on all four sides; today, small streams remain at the rear (west) and on part of the northern side as traces of these moats.

Although the origins of the Horiuchi family are uncertain, they appear in the historical record from around the mid-fifteenth century. From the mid-sixteenth century onward, around the time of Horiuchi Ujijoshi / Ujizen (reading uncertain) (reading of 氏善 uncertain), they expanded their power through ties with the shrine families of Kumano Hayatama and Kumano Nachi. During Hashiba Hideyoshi's campaign in Kii, they submitted to him and were permitted to govern the whole Kumano region. From participation in Hideyoshi's invasions of Korea to the transport of Kumano timber to Kyoto and Osaka, they exercised their authority from this place as their base until they joined the Western Army in the Battle of Sekigahara and fled to Kyushu.

This is a place where one can glimpse the history of Shingū before it was developed as the castle town of early modern Shingū Castle.

June 2020
Shingū City Board of Education

Appendix B. Ōzaki Shinryū Memorial Stone

Figure B1. Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone at Zenryū-ji. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Figure B2. Detail of the Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Figure B3. Detail of the Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Japanese text

尾崎卯右衛門
尾崎宗助ノ六男
文政三年九月二日新宮生ル
明治二十一年八月三十一日歿
虚靈山明暗寺役僧
虚無僧名 尾崎真龍

明暗真法流尺八開祖仰カル
法名 觀山了音信士
菩提寺 全龍寺
昭和五十三年秋吉日
淡交会南紀支部青年部建立
撰 稲垣衣白
書 杉本宗珠

下部小銘板：
紀宝町成川
村山謙造 刻

Romaji

Ōzaki Uemon
Ōzaki Sōsuke no roku-nan
Bunsei san-nen kugatsu futsuka Shingū umaruru
Meiji nijūichi-nen hachigatsu sanjūichi-nichi botsu
Kyoreizan Myōan-ji yakusō
Komusō-mei Ōzaki Shinryū
Myōan Shinpō-ryū shakuhachi kaiso aogaru
Hōmyō Kanzan Ryōon Shinji
Bodaiji Zenryū-ji
Shōwa gojūsan-nen aki kichijitsu
Tankōkai Nanki shibu seinenbu konryū
Sen Inagaki Ihaku
Sho Sugimoto Sōju

Kabu shōmeiban:
Kihō-chō Narukawa
Murayama Kenzō koku

Direct English translation

Ōzaki Uemon.
The sixth son of Ōzaki Sōsuke.
Born in Shingū on the second day of the ninth month of Bunsei 3 (1820).
Died on the thirty-first day of the eighth month of Meiji 21 (1888).
Yakusō of Kyoreizan Myōan-ji.
His Komusō name was Ōzaki Shinryū.
He is revered as the founding figure of the shakuhachi tradition of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū.
His posthumous Buddhist name was Kanzan Ryōon Shinji.
His memorial temple was Zenryū-ji.
Erected on an auspicious day in autumn, Shōwa 53 (1978),
by the Youth Division of the Nanki Branch of the Tankōkai.
Text composed by Inagaki Ihaku.
Calligraphy by Sugimoto Sōju.

Lower plaque:
Narukawa, Kihō-chō.
Engraved by Murayama Kenzō.

Appendix C. Grave-Site Signboard for Ōzaki Shinryū

Figure C1. Grave-site signboard for Ōzaki Shinryū near Shinmyō-ji. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Figure C2. Grave-site material near Shinryo-ji. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Figure C3. Grave-site material near Shinnyo-ji. Photograph by the author, June 2025.

Japanese text

尾崎真龍

文政三年（一八二〇）九月二日 紀伊国新宮に生まれる。
本名尾崎卯右衛門。元三〇〇石の紀州藩士。

幕末から明治初年にかけて、京都の明暗寺に伝わる尺八の本曲を
「明暗真法流」と称して奏し、尺八の名手として高名を得る。

高弟であった勝浦正山師に明暗寺伝来の五九曲の本曲を伝えたが、
この数は尺八の奏曲としては、おびただしい曲数であるという。

幕末には明暗寺が尊王志士の隠れ家となるなど尊王派に協力したため幕吏に捕えられ、
明治四年廃宗以後、故郷の新宮に幽閉され、明治二二年八月三十一日、七〇歳で没した。

Romaji

Ōzaki Shinryū

Bunsei san-nen (issen happyaku nijū) kugatsu futsuka, Kii no kuni Shingū ni umareru.
Honmyō Ōzaki Uemon. Moto sanbyaku-goku no Kishū-hanshi.

Bakumatsu kara Meiji shonen ni kakete, Kyōto no Myōan-ji ni tsutawaru shakuhachi no honkyoku o
“Myōan Shinpō-ryū” to shōshite sōshi, shakuhachi no meishu to shite kōmei o eru.

Kōtei de atta Katsuura Shōzan-shi ni Myōan-ji denrai no gojūkyoku no honkyoku o tsutaeta ga,
kono kazu wa shakuhachi no sōkyoku to shite wa, obitadashii kyokusū de aru to iu.

Bakumatsu ni wa Myōan-ji ga sonnō shishi no kakurega to naru nado sonnōha ni kyōryoku shita tame bakuri
ni toraerare,

Meiji yo-nen haishū igo, kokyō no Shingū ni yūhei sare, Meiji nijūni-nen hachigatsu sanjūichi-nichi,
nanajussai de botsu shita.

Direct English translation

Ōzaki Shinryū

He was born in Shingū in Kii Province on the second day of the ninth month of Bunsei 3 (1820). His real name was Ōzaki Uemon. He had formerly been a 300-koku retainer of the Kishū domain.

From the late bakumatsu period into the early Meiji years, he performed the shakuhachi honkyoku transmitted at Kyoto's Myōan-ji under the name "Myōan Shinpō-ryū," and gained renown as a master of the shakuhachi.

He transmitted fifty-nine honkyoku pieces inherited in the Myōan-ji tradition to his outstanding disciple Katsuura Shōzan; it is said that, as a shakuhachi performing repertory, this was an extraordinarily large number of pieces.

In the late bakumatsu, Myōan-ji became, among other things, a refuge for sonnō loyalists, and because he cooperated with the sonnō faction he was arrested by bakufu officials. After the abolition of the Fuke sect in the 4th year of Meiji (明治四年, 1871), he was confined in his hometown of Shingū. He died on August 31 in the 22nd year of Meiji (明治二十二年, 1889) at the age of 70.

Chronological note: the grave-side sign gives Meiji 22 (1889) and age seventy. This can be understood as traditional Japanese age reckoning (kazoe-doshi), since $1889 - 1820 + 1 = 70$. It therefore does not by itself prove that Ōzaki was seventy by modern Western age calculation. The discrepancy remains the year of death: the Zenryū-ji memorial stone gives Meiji 21 (1888), which is preferred in the main article because the stone is the stronger local memorial source.

Appendix D. Prosopographical Register

The register gives names in romanized form, followed by kanji in parentheses where appropriate. It is based on several kinds of evidence rather than on a single source tradition: Yukino Tomoko's work on the Shinpō manuscripts, Lee's correction of later Myōan-ji claims, the Zenryū-ji inscription, the grave-side materials documented in Shingū, Tsukamoto Kodō's 1978 report, the indirectly cited 1977 Geinō Shinpō notice on the grave rediscovery, Katsuura Seizan Ifu, and modern Japanese reference and catalogue records. These sources are not treated as equal. Some preserve inscriptional or manuscript evidence; others belong to later memorial or reference traditions. The entries therefore distinguish, as far as possible, between secure facts, probable reconstructions, and points that remain unresolved.

Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎真龍)

Ōzaki Shinryū is one of the central transmission figures in the historical formation of the later Myōan Shinpō tradition. Modern Japanese reference works identify him as a shakuhachi player born in 1820 in Shingū (新宮, Shingū), deceased in 1888, whose secular name was Ōzaki Uemon (尾崎卯右衛門 / 尾崎宇右衛門, Ōzaki Uemon). They further describe him as a disciple of Watanabe Kakuzan (渡辺鶴山), a functionary monk of Myōan-ji (明暗寺), and a teacher of Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山) and Kondō Sōetsu (近藤宗悦).

The strongest fixed point in the present study is the commemorative inscription at Zenryū-ji (全龍寺), which identifies him as "Ōzaki Uemon, sixth son of Ōzaki Sōsuke, yakusō of Kyoreizan Myōan-ji, Komusō name Ōzaki Shinryū, revered as founder of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū." This inscription is modern, not early Meiji, and therefore must be treated critically; however, it is highly important because it consolidates several core biographical claims in one coherent memorial source.

Yukino Tomoko's dissertation reinforces Ōzaki's importance by placing him within a manuscript-based transmission chain from Watanabe Kakuzan to Ōzaki Shinryū and then to Katsuura Shōzan. It presents him not simply as a legendary founder, but as a historically meaningful carrier of an older Kyoto Myōan repertorial layer. At the same time, the dissertation's overall method warns against taking later lineage constructions as transparent historical fact. In this respect, Ōzaki is best understood as a pivotal transmission figure whose role in the formation of the later Shinpō corpus is strong, even if not every later biographical detail can yet be verified from primary temple or domain records.

His title yakusō (役僧) is especially important. In general Japanese usage, this term means a monk entrusted with practical, administrative, or official temple functions, not necessarily the abbot or head priest. This supports the interpretation that Ōzaki was remembered as a functionary monk of Myōan-ji rather than as its securely documented abbot. This distinction matters because older shakuhachi literature sometimes inflated him into a numbered abbatial role, a construction that later scholarship, including Riley Lee, has treated critically.

Several dramatic details attached to Ōzaki in later biographical tradition remain unresolved. These include claims that he was politically active in sonnō circles, acted as a confidential courier between Edo and Kyoto, was arrested by the Bakufu, and was later confined in Kii/Shingū. These claims are widely repeated in later tradition and are cited in the transmission literature, but they still await confirmation from domain records, police materials, or contemporary local documentation. For the present, they should be treated as probable but not fully verified elements of modern Ōzaki biography.

Ōzaki Uemon (尾崎卯右衛門 / 尾崎宇右衛門)

Ōzaki Uemon is not a separate individual from Ōzaki Shinryū, but his secular name. This is confirmed by both modern Japanese reference works and the Zenryū-ji memorial inscription. The two principal forms in circulation are 尾崎卯右衛門 and 尾崎宇右衛門. The Zenryū-ji stone uses 卯右衛門, while reference literature often gives 宇(卯)右衛門, indicating orthographic variation in later transmission rather than a distinct person.

This distinction is prosopographically important because temple or lineage sources may preserve the religious/artistic name 尾崎真龍, whereas local, civil, or family materials may preserve only the secular name 尾崎卯右衛門 / 宇右衛門. Future archival work on family registers, removal registers, or local administrative records should therefore search for both forms.

Ōzaki Sōsuke (尾崎宗助, Ōzaki Sōsuke)

Ōzaki Sōsuke appears in the present study as the father of Ōzaki Shinryū. The Zenryū-ji commemorative inscription states that Ōzaki Shinryū was the sixth son of Ōzaki Sōsuke, and modern Japanese reference works independently describe him as the sixth son of a Shingū domain warrior of that name. This convergence makes the paternal identification strong, though still dependent on later memorial and reference tradition rather than on directly cited domain rosters.

No direct temple function is known for Ōzaki Sōsuke. His importance is social and genealogical: he locates Ōzaki Shinryū within a warrior family of the Shingū/Kii sphere and thereby complicates the simplistic image of Komusō as socially marginal wanderers. Nevertheless, the exact office, stipend, and domain rank of Ōzaki Sōsuke remain open. The often repeated claim that the family held 300 koku should not be treated as fully established until confirmed from a domain warrior roster, family register, or other official documentary source.

Watanabe Kakuzan (渡辺鶴山, Watanabe Kakuzan)

Watanabe Kakuzan is the figure identified in later transmission literature as the teacher of Ōzaki Shinryū. Modern reference works repeat this relation, and Yukino Tomoko's dissertation makes it central to its reconstruction of the Shinpō transmission. According to the dissertation, Watanabe Kakuzan served as a yakusō of Kyoto Myōan-ji between 1818 and 1829 and transmitted sixty pieces of the old Kyoto Myōan repertory to Ōzaki Shinryū.

This makes Watanabe Kakuzan a figure of major importance, but his documentation is still uneven. The teacher-student relation with Ōzaki is well established in later scholarly and reference tradition, yet primary temple records directly naming him in this capacity have not yet been produced in the present study. Likewise, although earlier shakuhachi historiography sometimes presented him as a numbered abbot of Myōan-ji, that type of abbatial numbering has been criticized by later scholarship and should not be repeated without direct institutional evidence. The safest formulation at present is that Watanabe Kakuzan was a Myōan-related functionary monk and transmission figure, probably of great importance, but not securely documented as abbot.

Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山)

Katsuura Shōzan is one of the clearest and most secure figures in the entire transmission chain. Modern Japanese reference works identify him as born in 1856 and deceased in 1942, with the secular name Katsuura Shigetarō (勝浦繁太郎). He is explicitly described as a disciple of Ōzaki Shinryū and as the recipient of the complete honkyoku corpus of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū. He later became head of the Kyoto branch of the Myōan Kyōkai (明暗教会京都支部長, Myōan Kyōkai Kyōto shibuchō).

In historical terms, Katsuura Shōzan is crucial because he stands at the point where the Ōzaki-associated transmission becomes institutionally visible in the modern period. Yukino Tomoko's dissertation strongly supports the view that the name "Shinpō-ryū" and, more fully, "Myōan Shinpō-ryū" became stabilized only at a later stage of transmission. Katsuura belongs precisely to that stage of consolidation. He is therefore not merely a passive disciple, but a major actor in the historical clarification, stabilization, and institutional legibility of the line.

Inagaki Ihaku (稲垣衣白)

Inagaki Ihaku is not part of the nineteenth-century transmission chain itself, but one of the most important twentieth-century mediators of the Ōzaki study. The National Diet Library identifies him as a modern editor and researcher, born in 1915 and deceased in 1995, associated with major shakuhachi and Myōan-related editorial work.

His role in the present study is particularly important because the commemorative inscription at Zenryū-ji is attributed to him. This means that Inagaki did not merely transmit received tradition but actively shaped the modern memorial presentation of Ōzaki Shinryū. He must therefore be treated as a major reconstructive authority in the modern historiography of Ōzaki, shakuhachi transmission, and Myōan memory. At the same time, his work belongs to the secondary and memorial layer of the evidence. It is highly valuable, but it should not be confused with contemporary nineteenth-century documentation.

Sugimoto Yoshio (杉本義夫)

Sugimoto Yoshio belongs, like Inagaki Ihaku, to the modern rediscovery layer rather than to the historical world of Ōzaki himself. In the present study he appears as a local Shingū figure connected with the rediscovery of

Ōzaki Shinryū's grave. Tsukamoto's 1978 ceremony report is now especially important because it identifies him as Sugimoto Yoshio (杉本義夫), also called Sōju (宗珠). This corresponds closely to the memorial inscription, which names Sugimoto Sōju (杉本宗珠) as the calligrapher of the stone. While his exact role in the earlier rediscovery article still depends on the still-uninspected Geinō Shinpō issue, the connection between Sugimoto Yoshio and the name Sōju is now strongly supported by Tsukamoto's dedication report.

Independent bibliographic evidence through CiNii also confirms that a person named Sugimoto Yoshio existed as a locally significant figure in the Shingū/Kumano region. This does not by itself prove his exact role in the Ōzaki rediscovery narrative, but it makes it highly plausible that he was a genuine local actor and not a fictive retrospective name. For the present, Sugimoto Yoshio should be described as a probable local historical informant or memory-bearer in Shingū who participated in or informed the twentieth-century recovery of Ōzaki Shinryū's burial site and local biography.

Relational Summary

The present evidence supports the following historical and historiographical structure. Ōzaki Sōsuke (尾崎宗助, Ōzaki Sōsuke) stands as the probable father of Ōzaki Uemon / Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎卯右衛門 / 尾崎真龍, Ōzaki Uemon / Ōzaki Shinryū). Ōzaki Shinryū is in later transmission literature the disciple of Watanabe Kakuzan (渡辺鶴山, Watanabe Kakuzan), who is remembered as a yakusō of Kyoto Myōan-ji. Ōzaki in turn is treated as the teacher of Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山, Katsuura Shōzan), who became one of the principal post-Fuke carriers of the line and helped render the Myōan Shinpō-ryū historically visible in the modern period. Parallel to this nineteenth-century transmission line stands a twentieth-century recovery layer in which Inagaki Ihaku (稲垣衣白, Inagaki Ihaku) and Sugimoto Yoshio (杉本義夫, Sugimoto Yoshio) played key roles in reconstructing and memorializing the biography of Ōzaki Shinryū in Shingū.

Methodological Note

The prosopographical register is intended as a source-critical appendix rather than as a lineage chart. Its purpose is to keep separate the layers that the main article brings into relation: manuscript-based music-historical analysis, later printed transmission literature, local commemorative epigraphy, field evidence from Shingū, and modern biographical reconstruction.

Yukino Tomoko's dissertation is especially important for this structure because it shows that the Shinpō tradition cannot be reduced to a simple founder story. Repertoire, notation, naming, and institutional self-definition changed over time. The persons listed above should therefore be read as actors situated in different historical layers: older Kyoto Myōan transmission, late and post-Fuke consolidation, and twentieth-century memorial reconstruction.

The Shingū materials add a second kind of evidence. The Zenryū-ji inscription, the grave-side signboard, the cemetery map, and Tsukamoto's 1978 ceremony report do not simply preserve facts from Ōzaki's lifetime; they also show how his biography was recovered, stabilized, and made public. For that reason the register marks, wherever possible, whether a claim is secure, probable, or still unresolved.

This method matches the conclusion of the article. Ōzaki Shinryū is not treated here as a transparent abbot-founder, nor as a merely legendary name, but as a figure reconstructed at the meeting point of temple memory, repertoire transmission, local field evidence, and later memorial work.

Appendix E. Chronology

Sacred and Topographical Background: Shingū, Kumano, and the Pilgrimage Routes

Before the nineteenth century.

Shingū formed part of the wider sacred landscape of Kumano Sanzan (熊野三山) and lay on major pilgrimage approaches now grouped under Kumano Kodō (熊野古道). In the Shingū area, four routes are especially relevant: Ogumotori-goe (大雲取越), Kogumotori-goe (小雲取越), Kōya-zaka (高野坂), and the river route down the Kumano-gawa (熊野川). This background is important because the local memorial landscape associated with Ōzaki Shinryū (尾崎真龍) was embedded not in an isolated provincial town, but in a long-established sacred and transit corridor centered on Kumano Hayatama Taisha (熊野速玉大社) and related Kumano sites.

Fifteenth to sixteenth centuries.

The site later occupied by Zenryū-ji (全龍寺) belonged to the former residence grounds of the Horiuchi family (堀内氏, Horiuchi-shi), a local power in the Oku-Kumano (奥熊野) region. According to the municipal explanatory signboard at the temple, the Horiuchi appear in the historical record from the mid-fifteenth century and expanded their influence in the sixteenth century through ties with the shrine families of Kumano Hayatama and Kumano Nachi. This is significant because the Ōzaki memorial stone stands in a precinct already marked by deep local political history.

1619–1633.

Shingū Castle (新宮城, Shingū-jō) was constructed in the early Edo period and served as the regional seat of the Mizuno family (水野家, Mizuno-ke) for ten generations. The castle overlooked the city and the Kumano-gawa, and formed the political framework within which later domain society in Shingū developed.

By 1875.

Shingū Castle had been dismantled in the early Meiji period. This point is chronologically important: the castle was not destroyed in the Second World War, but had already been removed by 1875 under early Meiji anti-castle policies.

Ōzaki Shinryū and the Late Myōan Environment

1819/1820.

The exact birth date of Ōzaki Shinryū remains slightly unstable in the sources, but the strongest local epigraphic evidence, namely the memorial stone at Zenryū-ji, gives Bunsei 3, ninth month, second day (文政三年九月二日), i.e. birth in 1820 at Shingū. Later Japanese discussion citing older printed research likewise places his birth in the Bunsei period and identifies his secular name as Ōzaki Uemon (尾崎卯右衛門).

Family background.

The Zenryū-ji memorial stone identifies him as Ōzaki Uemon, the sixth son (六男, roku-nan) of Ōzaki Sōsuke (尾崎宗助, Ōzaki Sōsuke). The grave-side pink sign further presents him as a former 300-koku warrior of the Kishū domain (三〇〇石の紀州藩士). That status claim should be treated as part of the later local memorial tradition unless corroborated by domain records, but the identification of Ōzaki as Uemon, sixth son of Ōzaki Sōsuke, is central to the modern reconstruction of his biography.

By the late Edo / bakumatsu period.

Ōzaki was remembered as “yakusō of Kyoreizan Myōan-ji” (虚靈山明暗寺役僧, Kyoreizan Myōan-ji yakusō). This wording, preserved on the Zenryū-ji memorial stone, is the strongest currently available local

evidence for his institutional affiliation with Myōan-ji (明暗寺). It does not prove that he was abbot, but it strongly supports the view that he occupied a formal temple function within the Myōan tradition.

1856.

Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山) was born. Later Japanese shakuhachi writing, as cited in modern discussion, gives his birth date as Ansei 3, sixth month, third day (安政三年六月三日).

Late bakumatsu (before 1868).

Later local and shakuhachi-oriented accounts connect Myōan-ji with pro-imperial sonnōha (尊王派, sonnōha) circles and state that Ōzaki was arrested by bakufu officials. At present, however, this remains a later memorial tradition rather than a fully secured archival fact. It should therefore be treated cautiously unless corroborated by earlier documentary evidence.

1868.

The end of the bakufu (幕府) and the beginning of Meiji rule form the broader political turning point for Ōzaki's world and for shakuhachi history more generally.

1871.

The Fuke sect (普化宗, Fuke-shū) was abolished. For the purposes of the present chronology, this marks the formal end of the institutional framework within which Myōan-ji had previously functioned. In line with Riley Lee's broader analysis of shakuhachi transmission, this moment should be understood less as the end of musical transmission than as the collapse of an older institutional order.

After 1871.

Later local narrative places Ōzaki back in Shingū under constrained circumstances, often described as yūhei (幽閉, yūhei) or confinement. Since this information presently comes through late commemorative and secondary channels, the safest formulation is that local tradition holds that, after the collapse of the old order, he returned to or remained in his native Shingū under restricted circumstances.

Transmission to Katsuura Shōzan and the Post-Myōan Formation of the School

1883–1887.

The most useful working chronology for the transmission from Ōzaki to Katsuura Shōzan places Shōzan's discipleship under Ōzaki between April 1883 and November 1887. Modern Japanese discussion citing Takahashi Kūzan (高橋空山) states that Shōzan studied under "Ōzaki Shinryū, who had been a yakusō of Kyoto Myōan-ji" and received the Myōan repertory correctly. This period should therefore be treated as the key window for the actual transmission of pieces from Ōzaki to Shōzan.

Transmission of the repertory.

The grave-side sign states that Ōzaki transmitted fifty-nine pieces (五九曲, gojūkyoku) to Katsuura Shōzan. Later shakuhachi-oriented Japanese discussion broadens this to "nearly seventy pieces" of the Myōan tradition. The safest formulation is that local and lineage-based sources consistently present Ōzaki as the major transmitter of a very substantial Myōan -derived repertory to Shōzan.

After 31 August 1888.

The repertorial core was inherited from Ōzaki, but the more sharply articulated school identity of the Myōan Shinpō-ryū (明暗真法流) appears to belong to the post-Fuke, and perhaps post-Ōzaki, situation. Later Japanese writing and earlier research cited within it suggest that Katsuura Shōzan (勝浦正山) was the key figure in shaping and naming the school more explicitly after the collapse of the old institutional order.

Death, Family, Grave, and Local Catastrophe

31 August 1888.

The strongest presently accessible evidence gives Ōzaki's death as Meiji 21, eighth month, thirty-first day (明治二十一年八月三十一日歿). This date appears on the Zenryū-ji memorial stone and is preferable to the contradictory date on the pink grave-side sign.

Wife and household.

Later Japanese discussion based on local research reports that Ōzaki's wife was Kane (かね, Kane) and that the household later involved an adopted heir, Otomatsu (音松, Otomatsu), rather than a securely attested biological son. A later report on the rediscovery of the grave describes the site as the joint grave of Ōzaki and his wife, whose posthumous name was Shūoku Myōrin Shinnyo (秋屋妙林信女). At present, however, the exact death dates of Ōzaki's wife and adopted heir are not secured in the accessible source base and should remain open unless further records are found.

1889.

The Totsukawa Flood (十津川大水害, Totsukawa daisuigai) devastated the Kumano river system. Official river-history sources report 175 deaths, 1,017 houses washed away or totally destroyed, and 524 houses partly destroyed. Methodologically, this is important because later local discussion suggests that temple records and registers in the area may have been lost in flood damage. The flood therefore belongs to the immediate post-Ōzaki memorial environment, not to his lifetime if the Meiji 21 death date is accepted.

Twentieth-Century School Memory and Local Rediscovery

1917 and 1922.

Later documentation associated with Katsuura Shōzan indicates that the line had become textually self-conscious by the Taishō period. A chronology cited in modern Japanese discussion notes the copying of a Komusō okitegaki (虚無僧掟書, Komusō okitegaki) in 1917 and a Shinpō-ryū shakuhachi onpu shirabe (真法流尺八音譜調) in 1922. These materials are important not as proof of Ōzaki's own terminology, but as evidence for the later textual consolidation of the line.

30 October 1942.

Katsuura Shōzan died, according to later Japanese shakuhachi tradition citing Takahashi Kūzan.

Modern Rediscovery of Grave and Biography

5 June 1977.

Later Japanese discussion reports that Sugimoto Yoshio (杉本義夫), a local historian in Shingū, discovered the joint grave of Ōzaki Shinryū and his wife. This discovery was reportedly announced in a newspaper article titled “Ōzaki Shinryū no haka, tsuini hakkensaru” (「尾崎真龍の墓 ついに発見さる」) in Geinō Shinpō (『芸能新報』, Geinō Shinpō), no. 263.

1977–1978.

According to the same reconstruction, Inagaki Ihaku (稲垣衣白) repeatedly contacted Shingū municipal authorities and, with the assistance of Sugimoto Yoshio, examined many removed household-register entries until Ōzaki Uemon was identified as the historical person behind Ōzaki Shinryū. This reconstruction is important because the resulting data closely match the wording of the Zenryū-ji memorial stone.

1978.

The memorial stone at Zenryū-ji was erected, as indicated by the inscription “an auspicious day in autumn,

Shōwa 53” (昭和五十三年秋吉日). The stone names Inagaki Ihaku as author of the inscription (撰 稲垣衣白), which makes it more than a local monument: it is also a document of the modern reconstruction of Ōzaki’s biography.

2 October 1978. Tsukamoto Kodō’s report describes the dedication and unveiling ceremony for the Ōzaki Shinryū memorial stone in Shingū. The ceremony brought together local Shingū figures, members of the Urasenke Tankōkai Nanki Branch, Myōan-related shakuhachi practitioners, and participants in komusō dress. The report is valuable for reconstructing the public memorial event, but its printed location 金竜寺町／金竜寺 is best treated as a probable error for Zenryū-ji (全龍寺).